

Dental Sealants and fluoride overview for caries prevention

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Abstract:

Dental caries has been the most common disease in childhood. The World Health Organization (WHO) emphasizes that dental caries affects about 60 to 90% of School children and the majority of adults. The patterns of dental caries globally and regionally reflect the risk profiles of countries relate to social structure, living conditions, and existence of preventive oral health systems. Moreover, a rising prevalence of early childhood caries has been reported. It has turned from a wealth-related disease into a disease of poverty. However, dental caries is a preventable disease and can be potentially reversed in its early stages. The importance of primary prevention has been emphasized in young children. The use of fluoride to increase resistance of teeth to caries development has been widely used. Mechanisms of fluoride are both topical and systemic, but the topical effect is the most important over the life span. A great amount of time had been dedicated to the studies of enamel Remineralization. The modern approach has been suggested that non-invasive treatment of early caries lesion by Remineralization has the potential to be the major advance in the clinical management of the disease. Within the prevention methods, dental sealants are still underused even though their efficacy is well documented. The aim of this review is to highlight practice guidelines for the correct use of sealants and fluorides.

Results:

Fluoride is the best established remineralization strategy compared to the other remineralization system. Fluoride being the main active ingredient of remineralizing agent is most effective in reversing early lesion at the tooth surface. In forming one unit of fluorapatite ($\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6\text{F}_2$), every 2 fluoride ions, 10 calcium ions and 6 phosphate ions are required to consequently limiting the net remineralization to occur due to the availability of calcium and phosphate. The remineralization effect of topical fluorides only attempts to reduce apatite dissolution than to promote mineralization of lost minerals and apatite crystals. Moreover, the fluoride dosage in children still raises a concern in the occurrence of dental fluorosis due to fluoride ingestion, which may exceed the maximum allowable dosage and intake recommended for children under the six years of age.

The clinician should know which patients need dental sealants and when, in particular high-risk subjects and pre-school children. Dentists should also be able to determine the best choice between the different sealant materials of the two main categories, resin based and glass ionomer sealants, with regard to their different properties, such as carries preventive effect, fluoride release and retention rate. Several dental resin based materials, including resin based dental sealants, contain the monomer bisphenol A diglycidylether methacrylate (Bis-GMA), of which Bisphenol A (BPA) is a component. The controversy about the possible toxicity of this synthetic chemical resin used to produce plastic products is long debated and, even if the amount of BPA released by dental sealants is well below the limit proposed by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency and the European Food Safety Authority, the risk of exposure, particularly for children, can be further reduces by precautionary measures.

Conclusion:

Modern approaches to early childhood caries have been advocated in the shift from surgical to early intervention and preventive measures and showed increased interest in recent years. Minimal intervention dentistry has been widely accepted and through appropriate treatment, early lesions can be arrested or remineralized. Different types of remineralizing agents such as fluoride, casein phosphopeptide amorphous calcium phosphate, tricalcium phosphate, arginine, silver diamine fluoride, and theobromine which are only of the few studied agents available in the market that have been proven to either arrest caries progression or reduce the tooth susceptibility to demineralization.

Dental sealants play an important role in preventing the onset and the development of dental cavities Even if the fluoride releasing resin sealants are better than glass ionomer, with regards to retention of the material, the literature shows that their effectiveness in preventing fissure caries in permanent molars does not differ significantly over 24 months.

MIH and PEIR in dentistry: Diagnosis and treatment options

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Abstract:

The aim of this lecture is to report the diagnostic features, prevalence, mineral content, clinical significance and treatment options of MIH and PEIR, in order to minimize miss-treatment of primary and permanent teeth in young children.

MIH (Molar Incisor Hypomineralization) was defined as the occurrence of a hypomineralization of one to four permanent first molars from a systemic origin and frequently associated with affected incisors. Pre-eruptive intracoronal lesions (PEIR) are lesions that are located in the occlusal portion of the crown of unerupted permanent or primary teeth.

The prevalence of MIH was reported between 2.5-40% in the permanent first molars and 0-21.8% in primary second molars. PEIR was observed in 2-8% of children, mainly in mandibular second premolars and second and third permanent molars. A number of possible causes for MIH were mentioned, including environmental changes, diet and genetics in prenatal and postnatal periods, but all are questionable.

In PEIR, the resorption of the intracoronal dentine begins only after crown development is complete and is caused by osteoclast like giant cells observed histologically on the pulpal surface of the dentine. The mineral content in MIH is reduced in comparison to normal enamel and dependent on the severity of the lesion. In PEIR the resorbed surface of enamel showed less mineral content. The hypomineralized enamel in MIH is not suitable for restorations with amalgam or composite materials, and the best material should be based on remineralization material like glass-ionomers. Similar, the resorbed dentin surface in PEIR should be covered by the biocompatible and re-mineralizing glass-ionomer cement.

Figure 1: MIH with breakdown of enamel (left) and PEIR (right).

Effects of Swedish massage on blood pressure.

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Abstract:

Swedish massage technique includes mechanically activated muscular tissue and also skin, tendons, fascias, and connected tissue, which indirectly regulates the tonus of the autonomous nervous system. This study set out to examine the effects of Swedish massage on blood pressure. Healthy males were given massage treatment at the Karolinska Hospital, Stockholm, Sweden. Treatment was over a 12-week period divided into three parts, each consisting of 4 weeks. Two treatment periods contained massage treatment either on back, neck and chest (BNC), or leg, arm and face (LAF), with an in between washout period. The first treatment period with massage decreased systolic blood pressure directly after treatment (BNC: $P < 0.005$, LAF: $P < 0.01$), but no significant changes were seen in diastolic blood pressure. In the second period, BNC massage decreased systolic ($P < 0.005$) and diastolic ($P < 0.005$) blood pressure whereas LAF massage ($P < 0.05$) increased systolic blood pressure. Swedish massage on the BNC resulted in a minor decrease in blood pressure possibly due to sympathetic inhibition. It may be suggested that massage may be tried as a complementary therapy in patients suffering from increased blood pressure due to stress.

A Tale of Green and Pink (Effects of Green Tea in Oral Cancer): A Review

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Abstract:

Tea is one of the most ancient and popular beverages consumed around the world. It is made from the leaf of plant *Camellia sinensis*. It is divided into three types based on the fermentation process. Green tea (non-fermented), Oolong tea (semi-fermented), and Black tea (fermented). Consumption of tea, especially green tea, has been associated with many health benefits including cancer prevention. Some epidemiological observations have revealed that there was an inverse correlation between increased green tea intake and relative risk for cancers. The primary goal of chemoprevention here is to reverse, suppress, or inhibit the progression of premalignant lesions to cancer. Using green tea extracts (GTE)/ polyphenols in chemoprevention of oral premalignant lesions along with the use of GTE as a chemo preventive agent in various other cancers as well. It is proved by research for more than a decade that green tea polyphenols influence a number of pathways that are relevant to tumor growth proliferation and metastasis. The need of the hour for chemoprevention using green tea is development and validation of biomarkers that can be evaluated by clinical trials in a clinical setting. “The problem with a lot of chemotherapy drugs is that they really just target rapidly dividing cells, so cancer divides rapidly, but so do cells in your hair follicles and intestines”, “But you don’t see these sorts of side effects with green tea consumption”.

Keywords :

Green Tea Extracts (GTE); Polyphenols; Pre-Malignant Lesions and Chemoprevention.

Can Dental Hygienists Deal with Medical Emergencies? A Cross Sectional Study

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Abstract:

A medical emergency is a life-threatening situation that requires immediate interference. Knowledge and practice are the keys in managing a medical emergency. The most medical emergency occurred in dental hygiene settings is Hypoglycemia, as found that KSA ranked as the highest prevalence globally with percentage 17.6% in Diabetes Mellitus¹. Medical emergencies in dental clinics are commonly occurred after administering local anesthesia or during the dental treatment. Some situations are more likely to occur due to increased level of stress and anxiety which is often present and may cause medical emergencies such as syncope and hyperventilation. Therefore, basic life support, checking the availability of essential emergency drugs and equipment can reduce the morbidity or mortality. Most medical emergencies in dental and dental hygiene clinics are considered mild whereas the life-threatening situations are rare. Preventing medical emergencies can be through a good practice and preparation in handling these situations. First is by checking the whole vital signs and second is by taking a comprehensive medical history for every patient. Therefore, CPR should be performed to manage these situations and having the ability in giving or injecting the medical emergency drugs to the patient. We noticed from the previous studies^{2, 3} that they had been concentrating on dentists regardless on dental hygienists. Due to the lack, this cross sectional study is carried out to assess the ability of Dental Hygienists in managing medical emergencies in dental

Keywords :

Medical emergencies, dental hygienist, dental clinics, awareness, management, preparedness

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